

Alpha Activity in EEG and Intelligence

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ABSTRACT

Intelligence of a human being in general is considered as to its variations in the ability to learn, to function in society, and to behave according to contemporary social expectations Intelligence of a human being is associated with brain the brain is considered as the most complex biological existent structure. Electroencephalograph (EEG) is an instrument used for recording the electrical activity of the brain. EEG is the variation of the electrical fields in the cortex or on the surface of scalp caused by the physiological activities of the brain. EEG is currently the most widely adopted method for assessing brain activities. Detecting the changes of these waves is critical for understanding of brain function. In clinical applications, spontaneous EEG signals can be divided into several rhythms according to their frequency. They are δ rhythm (0.1-4Hz), θ rhythm (4-8Hz), α rhythm (8-13), β and rhythm (13-30Hz). The EEG signals have close relationships with the cerebral diseases, mental status and human qualities like intelligence. As a consequence it is very useful to analyze process and classify the EEG signal on the basis of frequency bands and then extract their underlying features and so as to correlate with normal and abnormal functioning of brain, sleep, mental status and also with intelligence. In this paper we propose to conduct pointed literature survey of alpha activity and intelligence correlation. We propose to conduct test on subjects by computer, EEG interface. We propose to conclude from practical experimentation, whether there is a correlation between alpha activity power and intelligence.

KEYWORDS

EEG (Electroencephalography), IQ (Intelligence Quotient), FFT (Fast Fourier Transform).

1. INTRODUCTION

EEG activity in 13-15 bands was studied by Paterson M.B; Cluck h, Mack JL and found correlation with intelligence D Posthuma, M.C Neale, D.I Boomsma, and EJC Degeus have studied correlation between alpha peak and intelligence. The encyclopedia Britannica gives various theories of intelligence starting from Herbert Spencer Francin Galton etc have defined intelligence as ability to carry out abstract thinking in the book “the making of intelligence” Ken Richardson has pointed out various definitions of intelligence and measurement of IQ. He has

also pointed out that the origin of intelligence is in the brain and it can be proved experimentally. He points out various philosophers like Plato, Australia, Gabriel Murfy etc defining intelligence. The IQ was proposed by German scientist William Stern as below:

$$IQ = \frac{\text{Mental Age}}{\text{Chronological Age}} \times 100$$

The book “Mega brain” by Michel Hutson gives techniques how intelligence is proved. He gives the instrumental method. Norbert Fauovec claims that experiments have proved that alpha activity power is more with gifted persons.

2.1 DEFINING INTELLIGENCE

Most people have an intuitive notion of what intelligence is, and many words in the English language distinguish between different levels of intellectual skills, bright, dull smart, stupid, and clever, slow, and so on. Yet no universally accepted definition of intelligence exists and people continue to debate what, exactly, it is. Fundamental questions remain: Is intelligence one’s general ability or several independent systems or abilities? Is intelligence a property of the brain, a characteristic of behavior, or a set of knowledge and skills? The simplest definition proposed is that intelligence is whatever intelligence tests measure. But this definition does not characterize the ability well, and it has several problems. First it is circular: The tests are assumed to verify the existence of intelligence tests exist, and they do not all measure the same thing. In fact, the maker’s measure. Finally, the definition says very little about the specific nature of intelligence. Abilities are as follows Visual-Arithmetic- Spelling. These separate scores are spastically analyzed, and from them a general intelligence quotient.

TABLE 1: FREQUENCY RANGES OF DIFFERENT EEG ACTIVITY

EEG Activity	Lower Frequency	Upper Frequency
Delta	0	4
Theta	4	8
Alpha	8	13
Beta	13	30

We have collected data of number of subjects and computed IQ from written tests. We have separated $\alpha, \beta, \delta, \theta$. We have computed percentage power. We have tried to compare percentage power of $\alpha, \beta, \delta, \theta$ with IQ, relative IQ. We have calculated difference of alpha power and IQ. The results are interesting.

2. ALGORITHM

Programming is dividing into three parts

- I) Taking the EEG waves
- II) Calculate the Relative power for all waves
- III) Calculate the % Difference with IQ & KIQ

$$Sum(1) = \sum_{\text{Delta lower}}^{\text{Delta upper}} Mg(k)$$

$$Sum(2) = \sum_{\theta_{lower}}^{\theta_{upper}} Mg(k)$$

$$Sum(3) = \sum_{\alpha_{lower}}^{\alpha_{upper}} Mg(k)$$

$$Sum(4) = \sum_{\beta_{lower}}^{\beta_{upper}} Mg(k)$$

$$Sum(0) = Mg(0) + \dots + Mg(N - 1)$$

Where $\Delta_{lower} = \Delta_{lower} * N/Fs$
 $\Delta_{Higher} = \Delta_{higher} * N/Fs$

2.1 PROCEDURE

The students of Engineering are having good intelligence, hence student of mentally retarded school, subjects with various abnormalities in the brain are collected. The data collection is done for 1 hour continuous record of EEG using Polysomnography.

2.1.1 PERCENTAGE POWER CALCULATION

After applying the FFT to an EEG signal, the magnitude values are stored for each band. The lower cut of frequency and upper cut of frequency is defined depending upon the frequency range of each band. Only the signals between the upper band and lower band of EEG remain as they are. The graphical results for each band like Delta, Alpha, Beta and Theta are calculated as follows:

$$\theta_{higher} = \theta_{higher} * N/Fs$$

$$\theta_{Lower} = \theta_{lower} * N/Fs$$

$$\alpha_{lower} = \alpha_{lower} * N/Fs$$

$$\alpha_{higher} = \alpha_{higher} * N/Fs$$

$$\beta_{Lower} = \beta_{lower} * N/Fs$$

$$\beta_{higher} = \beta_{higher} * N/Fs$$

Where

$Fs =$ Sampling Frequency (250Hz)

$N =$ N Point DFT

Percentage power in each band is calculated as:

$$\Delta_{percentage\ power} = Sum(1)/Sum(0)$$

$$\theta_{percentage\ power} = Sum(2)/Sum(0)$$

$$\alpha_{percentage\ power} = Sum(3)/Sum(0)$$

$$\beta_{percentage\ power} = Sum(4)/Sum(0)$$

3. INTELLIGENCE STANDARD

The time, weight, length etc. have the international standards based on comparison with standard parameters. Similarly unless a base of intelligence is assumed the relative measurement of intelligence cannot be done. For this purpose Prof. S.G. Kahalekar's alpha activity is considered unit, i.e. 100. The comparative KIQ can be direct unit of intelligence parameter.

Figures in Table 2 show how Alpha activity is dominating all other activities in all montages, which is termed as Relative Power Frequency Band. Bar graph shown in Figure 1.4 gives the comparison between different Alpha activity, IQ and the KIQ and shows the clear cut relation between alpha activity and the IQ; also it shows the IQ level of subject with respect to KIQ. Bar graphs in figure 1.5 and 1.6 give us an idea of individual subject's IQ levels and KIQ level respectively. Figures in table 3 & 4 shows us how the percentage power of alpha activity is related to the performance of the subjects in their SSC exams. From table 5 relations between all the parameters which were being considered for the analysis is getting clear, which gives a broad picture of relationships between Alpha activity, SSC marks, IQ and KIQ. Percentage difference between alpha activity and SSC marks is shown by table 6, from which it is clear that difference is acceptable and our technique is not far away from the accuracy. And at last table 7 gives us the comparison between all the parameters of 20 subjects, which is self explanatory in explaining the relationship between IQ of person and his/her power of alpha activity.

TABLE 2: RELATIVE POWER FREQUENCY BAND

MONTAGES	DELTA	THETA	ALPHA	BETA
FP2-F4	2.2	20.1	61.2	16.5
F4-C4	0.6	25.5	71.3	2.6
C4-P4	15	14.4	49.9	20.6
P4-O2	5	23.1	66.1	5.8
O2-A2	1.3	3.3	87.8	7.6
A2-F2	2.9	17.4	56.5	23.1
F2-T6	2.4	32.4	61.7	3.5
T6-O2	4.3	10.3	49.9	35
FP1-P3	4.5	16.3	71.8	2.4
F3-C3	1.9	17.4	57.5	23.1
C3-P3	4.5	16.3	70.8	8.4

P3-O1	1	23.1	66.1	9.8
T3-T5	1.6	24.5	71.3	2.6
T5-O1	2.9	13.4	60.5	23.1
O1-A2	3.2	12.5	59.5	24.8
FP2-F8	1.8	14.6	55.8	27.3
F8-T4	2.4	25.8	57.5	14.5

Fig.1.4 Bar Graph for Alpha, IQ, KIQ

Fig.1.5 IQ Percentage

Fig.1.6 KIQ Percentage

Fig.1.7 % Difference b/w Alpha & KIQ

Fig.1.8 % Difference b/w Alpha & KIQ (P-20)

TABLE 3: MAX. % POWER OF ALPHA ACTIVITY BY PSG OF 5 SUBJECTS.

S.N.	PATIENT NAME	MAX. % POWER OF ALPHA ACTIVITY BY POLYSMOGRAPHY
1	PT-1	85.6
2	PT-2	72.3
3	PT-3	65.8
4	PT-4	50.2
5	PT-5	48.7

TABLE 4: MAX. % POWER OF ALPHA ACTIVITY COMPARED WITH SSC MARKS

S.N.	COMPUTED MAX.ALPHA ACTIVITY POWER	SSC MARKS	% DIFFERENCE
1	85.4	83	2.4
2	72.0	71	1
3	65.5	63	2.5
4	50.1	55	4.9
5	48.9	50	1.1

TABLE 5: POWER OF ALPHA ACTIVITY COMPARED WITH IQ, SSC MARKS, AND KIQ

S.N.	IQ	SSC	KIQ	ALPHA POWER
<u>1</u>	80	83	84.6	85.6
<u>2</u>	73	71	76	72.3
<u>3</u>	67	63	61.8	65.8
<u>4</u>	50	55	46	50.2
<u>5</u>	43	50	48.1	48.7

TABLE 6: MAX. % POWER OF ALPHA ACTIVITY COMPARED WITH SSC MARKS

S.N.	MAX. % POWER OF ALPHA ACTIVITY BY POLYSMOGRAPHY	SSC MARKS	%DIFFERENCE
1	85.6	83	2.6
2	72.3	71	1.3
3	65.8	63	2.8
4	50.2	55	4.8
5	48.7	50	1.3

TABLE: 7 GRAPHICAL RESULTS OF ALPHA ACTIVITY AND INTELLIGENCE

S. No.	NAME OF A SUBJECT	RELATIVE POWER FREQUENCY BAND				SSC MARK	I Q	KIQ	% DIFFERENCE	
		DELTA	TETA	ALPHA	BETA				IQ-ALPHA	KIQ-ALPHA
P-1	Prof.S.G.Kahaleka	02.2	20.1	61.2	16.6	70	80	100	18.2	38.2
P-2	Monalika Nagesh	00.6	25.5	71.3	02.6	58	58	72.2	13.3	0.9
P-3	Umer Pasha	15.0	14.4	49.9	20.6	60	60	75.0	10.4	25.1
P-4	Mandale Pramod	01.3	03.3	87.8	07.6	77	77	96.2	10.8	8.4
P-5	Bharti Gajanan	05.0	23.1	66.1	05.8	75	75	93.5	8.9	27.2
P-6	Rakhonde Nilesh	02.9	17.4	56.5	23.1	50	50	62.2	6.5	5.7
P-7	Abdul Wahab	02.4	32.4	61.7	03.5	72	72	90.0	10.3	28.3
P-8	Abdul Naeem	04.3	10.3	49.9	36.0	64	64	80.0	14.1	30.1
P-9	Sardeshpande A.S	04.5	16.3	76.8	02.4	80	70	87.5	6.8	10.7
P-10	Ganesh Rathod	01.9	17.4	57.5	23.1	58	58	72.5	0.5	14.7
P-11	Atar Imran K	04.5	16.3	70.8	08.4	62	62	73.5	8.8	6.7
P-12	Mhatre Pranal	01.0	23.1	66.1	09.8	64	64	60.0	2.1	13.9
P-	Man Mohan Singh	03.0	18.1	66.2	11.7	62	62	71.5	4.2	11.3

13										
P-14	Landgu Mohan	02.4	28.4	61.7	07.5	64	64	82.0	2.3	18.3
P-15	Tolnur Prashant	01.6	24.5	71.3	02.6	58	58	62.2	13.3	0.19
P-16	Kadve Sachin	02.9	13.4	60.5	23.1	60	60	75.5	0.5	24.5
P-17	Saleem choudry	03.2	24.5	59.3	26.8	78	50	62.2	13.3	10.3
P-18	D.Altaf khan	01.8	14.6	65.8	27.3	78	80	70.0	10.4	15.7
P-19	Nayeem Ahmed M	02.4	25.8	57.5	32.5	81	80	80.0	10.8	6.17
P-20	Syed Mujstar	04.1	32.6	65.8	35.3	74	75	87.5	8.9	23.9

4. CONCLUSION

The α activity can be measured using latest instruments. The literature supports the correlation of α activity with intelligence. The data recorded also supports correlation between α activity and human intelligence. Hence we conclude that the Alpha activity has more correlation (less % Difference) as compared to other waves. Alpha activity is related is to Intelligence Quotient. The tables show only few results. Actually 200 subject test data is available. In Table 7.5 Relative Power Frequency Band, alpha activity is calculated by FFT. We observe that the power of alpha activity is maximum as the subject is in alert and awake state, more over the power of alpha activity is maximum in O2-A2. Thus we conclude that the alpha activity is responsible for intelligence, and is dominant at all points in a awake and alert person and is at maximum at O2-A2.

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